

A taxonomy for cybersecurity standards applicable to the maritime sector

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The current crisis (climate change, COVID-19 pandemic outbreak, Russia's invasion of Ukraine) has led to serious atrocities, and humanitarian and financial disasters to societies and industries; our critical infrastructures, systems and operations became even more vulnerable to cyber-attacks due to lack of compliance with cybersecurity standards, missing controls, disaster recovery and business continuity plans.

Modern interconnected ICT infrastructures consist of cyber-physical systems which are highly digitally-dependent and thus have become more vulnerable to cyber attacks. Thus, the lack of compliance with appropriate security standards on these systems can exponentially facilitate the hard consequences previously mentioned due to a series of rising cybersecurity challenges¹. For instance, threat actors are continuously evolving their skills and they may easily find available next-generation malware toolkits (e.g. Ransomware-as-a-service models²) throughout the Internet (e.g. Deep and Dark Web) allowing them to launch sophisticated cyber attacks (e.g. supply chain attacks, APT attacks and data breaches, such as the 2022 Telegram's leak³). The advanced cyber attacks may be activated by misled people to provide personal information with phishing e-mails or exploiting security misconfigurations on systems and unpatched cloud opportunities. Moreover, modern war diplomacy is supported by cyber attacks to target states and federal agencies to sabotage Intelligence and steal the enemy's plans or leak information on policymakers' intentions or cause chaos to public and private organizations (e.g. SolarWinds attacks⁴) to disrupt economies. Nevertheless, attacks, such as the Colonial Pipeline ransomware affecting gasoline and jet fuel operations could lead instead of economic disaster to serious environmental harm and vice versa extreme weather conditions may cause physical disasters (e.g. power outage) generating weaknesses in critical infrastructures and increasing the potential of cyber intrusion. From this angle, attention is needed to considerably increase the investment on new methodologies that will help enterprises to ensure the compliance of their systems with appropriate cybersecurity standards. Compliance with cybersecurity standards is the basic cybersecurity practice that a critical sector (e.g. the maritime which operates essential services according to the NIS 2 Directive⁵) shall ensure.

How cybersecurity management could be sufficient and effective in the Maritime domain to address the security requirements? Standard is considered a level of quality or attainment something used as a measure, norm, or model in comparative evaluations. The confirmation that an organisation applies to all security requirements addressed by a security standard is validated through certification. Specifically, certification of an information security management system of an organisation, is one means of providing assurance that an entity has implemented a system for the management of the relevant aspects of its activities, products and services, in line with the entity's policy and the requirements of the corresponding international

¹ <https://www.checkpoint.com/cyber-hub/cyber-security/what-is-cybersecurity/biggest-cybersecurity-challenges-in-2022/#>

² <https://www.cm-alliance.com/cybersecurity-blog/the-rise-of-ransomware-as-a-service-in-2022>

³ <https://www.hackread.com/personal-details-supervpn-geckovpn-users-telegram-leaked/>

⁴ <https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/feature/SolarWinds-hack-explained-Everything-you-need-to-know>

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A823%3AFIN>

management system standard. In addition, security certification is assumed a measure for mitigating risks and facing threats identified either in organisational or sectorial or supply chain level that aims to add value in trust of the consumer⁶. In this light, maritime transport CII operators' conformance to security standards is a focal point to strengthen their resilience towards malevolent activities both proactively and reactively. Therefore, they may be used as cybersecurity shield vectors, either to leverage the knowledge on cyber attacks techniques and increase the level of projection and means of prevention of incursions on their CIIs or to study and assess the cascading effects and risk propagation over maritime transport interconnected CIIs in view of a cyber attack implementation and improve incident handling procedures and decision making to eliminate the damage as possible. To this end, the conformity cybersecurity certification is based on cybersecurity standards requirements and cybersecurity standards are the cornerstone to applying sufficient and effective security management on CIIs.

Security Risk Assessment (RA) is the process utilized to analyse and evaluate the security risks, threats and vulnerabilities of CIIs aiming to develop and implement a risk management plan and treat the discovered risks. Conformity Assessment (CA) is considered the process of evaluating whether specified requirements, rules or claims associated with an ICT product, ICT service or ICT process have been fulfilled, according to the Cybersecurity Act⁷. The synergy of both processes may lead to attest security specification and provide efficient mitigation measures that may advance CIIs resistance to attacks and boost their robustness. To achieve this, the interrelation of concepts needs to be clarified along with the multi-use of respective methodologies. In this vein, information security flows and conformity flows and their relations to standardization need to be identified and analysed. Following this direction, hybrid methodologies, such as the proposed Risk and Conformity Assessment of the EU H2020 project "CYRENE", aim to serve a dual scope, either assessing risks and developing a security profile of supply chain services or checking the conformance of these services⁸ to ensure their security and explore if they are subject to certification.

Currently, the list of standards supporting both security and conformity aspects on a global scale is exhaustive, appealing to several topics, such as IT evaluation, security requirements, risk management, technical specifications, etc.. This great range of topics is hindering CII operators to examine and determine which standards best fit to capture the specific needs of their organization or the entire supply chain, such as the maritime transport chain. Within this context, ENISA has recently published a report on the analysis of standardisation requirements in support of cybersecurity policy⁹. This report addresses published standards of different aspects of risk management and subsequently describes methodologies and tools that can be utilized to conform with or implement these standards.

Following this approach, this work provides a taxonomy of prominent international standards, best practices and guidelines related to information security management and security conformance. Specifically, the taxonomy is built on thematic groups according to their main topic of interest considering the security management requirements. The ultimate goal is to facilitate CII operators, such as those of the maritime transport domain, involving industries and organisations to identify more easily prominent standards related to information security management and security conformance according to different IT/OT and sector-specific aspects. The current taxonomy will allow them to better comprehend their purpose and improve their decision-making about selecting the most appropriate standards to apply concerning their security requirements. The taxonomy sets up the following ten (10) pillars:

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/61651.html>

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

⁸ <https://www.cyrene.eu/concept/>

⁹ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/risk-management-standards/@@download/fullReport>

1. **Vocabulary and Conceptualization.** The current pillar addresses terminologies and description of concepts associated with information security and conformity. It can be utilized by all the other categories.
2. **Security Requirements.** This category of standards illustrates all the information regarding the existing requirements of the security topic that needs to be addressed by the interested party, to improve and maintain the security.
3. **Security Guidelines.** It provides good practices to consult organisations and guide them how to address the requirements specified on standards of the previous category.
4. **Security Evaluation and Assessment.** This category embraces standards and good practices related to assessment methodologies or approaches provided that can be utilized by organisations as a means to evaluate if the security requirements standards of the corresponding category are met.
5. **Privacy and data protection.** It engages EU law and standards related to the maintenance of privacy and data protection.
6. **Risk Management standards.** It embraces standards and good practices that provide principles, frameworks or processes related to security risk management.
7. **Technical standards.** It contains standards and methodologies addressing technical security aspects, such as network security, encryption, blockchain, security architecture, communication, secure quantum technologies, and disruptive and emerging developments.
8. **AI & security.** It encloses standards, frameworks and good practices related to AI security under two perspectives: utilizing AI technologies to secure systems and securing AI systems.
9. **Sector-specific (i.e. Maritime Transport).** This category encompasses legal background, standards, processes and methods of security management that support the specific requirements and specificities of sector-specific (i.e. maritime transport.) CIIs.
10. **Critical Infrastructure Protection.** As building an ecosystem of resilient infrastructures is the ultimate goal of all modern economies, the current division targets at directives, frameworks and practices related to the protection of infrastructures that are critical for the sustainability of the economy and social well-being.

The proposed taxonomy is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 1 – Taxonomy of cybersecurity standards and best practices.

Using the ten (10) pillars, we categorize the cybersecurity standards, best practices and fundamental directives. Specific standards for the maritime sector can be found in the sector-specific pillar. With this taxonomy, we aim in helping enterprises finding standards and best practices to apply to specific needs.

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